

TAQLID SO‘ZLARNING SHAKLIY-STRUKTUR TAHLILI
(SIX CHAPTERS EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY OF THE LANGUAGE IS AN
EXAMPLE)

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Annotation. In this article, words included in the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” published in 2023 were studied without any reference to the category and words belonging to the category of onomatopoeic words were selected from among them. Based on the interpretation of words, illustrative examples and common meaning, explanations of the part of speech of imitation were given, illustrated based on examples and a list was provided for inclusion as a part of speech of imitation in subsequent editions of explanatory dictionaries with a special reference. Based on the data and conclusions obtained from the analysis of onomatopoeic words included without links in the 2023 edition, additional information and recommendations for subsequent editions of the explanatory dictionary were provided.

Keywords. Imitation words, repeated imitation words, imitation of sound, imitation of situation, illustrative example, explanation, difference.

Purpose of research

The emergence and development of languages, as well as their manifestation in different forms in different segments of society, necessitated the creation of dictionaries. A number of innovations in the field of lexicography have also stimulated the development of Uzbek linguistics. Our linguists are creating encyclopedic and linguistic, as well as monolingual and multilingual dictionaries containing various descriptions of words, which are constantly being updated.

The great changes taking place in all spheres of life of our republic, the strengthening of relations with many developed countries, have had a significant impact on the development of the Uzbek language, in particular, its lexicon, in a short period of time. Under the influence of such factors, in connection with serious changes in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language, work is underway to compile and publish a multi-volume explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language that meets the requirements of the time.

Onomatopoeic words are of great importance in our language. These words are significant because they reflect sounds and states emanating from all categories of objects and physical phenomena through human speech organs. The use of onomatopoeic words in written literature and colloquial speech shows the attractiveness of the text, its attractiveness, realism, originality and the limitless possibilities of our language. Currently, a number of achievements related to onomatopoeic words have been made in existing explanatory dictionaries. In particular, we can acknowledge that a significant number of onomatopoeic words are actively used in our language, that they are in tune with the times, that there are onomatopoeic words related to the literary language, as well as dialects, that many onomatopoeic words are given illustrative examples with a clear source. But due to the constant change of words, their connection with social life, the need to constantly introduce innovations into them will always remain. When new variants of some

words appear, changes occur in the meaning of some words. All this is a phenomenon connected with social life.

To date, comprehensive scientific research has been conducted and is being studied on the topic of onomatopoeic words, however, onomatopoeic words included in the “Explanatory Dictionaries of the Uzbek Language” have not been comparatively studied in the lexicographical aspect and scientific research on the semantization of onomatopoeic words has not been published.

The purpose of the research is to study the words belonging to the part of the original onomatopoeic word, included without a special reference in the explanatory dictionary published in 2023 and to develop recommendations for subsequent editions of the explanatory dictionary.

Research methods

When we studied the analysis of onomatopoeic words in explanatory dictionaries, we noticed the need for further improvement of lexicographic descriptions. When presenting onomatopoeic words in dictionaries, paying more attention to the situation and place of their use, as well as the presentation of excerpts from texts containing onomatopoeic words, ensures the purity of speech, facilitates the understanding of onomatopoeic words and increases the perfection of dictionaries.

In this article, a list of words belonging to the original onomatopoeic word class, included without a special reference in the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” published in 2023, was formed and they were analyzed in statistical, semantic and comparative aspects. For example, **AR-AR** To wail, to weep loudly. In the 2023 edition, this word is limited to a compound explanation. No synonyms or illustrative examples included. This word is widely used in the common language to denote the process of capriciousness caused by the inability of young children to control themselves.

BEZ-BEZ To get sick. *Turay deyman, oyog'im bez-bez qilib, turolmayman.* H.Nazar. Yonar dunyo. *Bu boshning zirqirashi haroratniki emas, tosh tegib zaharlangandek, allaqanday bez-bez qilmoqda.* S.Abdulla, Soyalar. *Ulfatlari yuz o'girdi, qoldi yolg'iz, ota-ona yuraklari qilar bez-bez.* The simple form of this lexeme belongs to the noun and expresses the meaning of objectivity. Most nouns are directly repeated and transition into adverbs. However, the fact that the lexeme **bez-bez** expresses imitation of mental, agonizing, painful situations through illustrative examples can be the basis for evaluating it not as an adverb, but as an imitative part of speech.

BILANG-BILANG To twitch. *Baliqday bilang-bilang qilib, goh unisi o'zib ketadi, goh bunisi.* H.Nazir, Yonar daryo. From the description given to the lexeme, it is difficult to understand its meaning; in the illustrative example, it is connected with the verb and expresses the manner of action. In this respect, it resembles the adverb of the state. However, it is correct to consider imitation as a part of speech, since it is named by imitation in the style of **bilang-bilang**, denoting the attractive, wavy state of fish when swimming, as well as because it is close to the category of imitative words such as **lik-lik, likang-likang, lapang-lapang**.

BILJING-BILJING To make a fuss. To talk too much, to chatter, to exaggerate inappropriate words. *Bir bedavo ezma, chakagiga suyangan ekan, Zuhraning uyidagi ahvoli, mashg'ulotini surishtirib, biljing-biljing qiladi.* A.Muhiddin, Aybsiz aybdor. This lexeme is rarely used in the general population, its meaning and place of occurrence are unfamiliar to many. It is observed in written sources, works of art, or in some dialects. Since the meaning expresses imitation of the situation when talking nonsense, it is advisable to consider imitation as a word.

GUPPA 1 With force. [Nodir] *Bir nafas ko 'ksini ochib, ayvon panjarasiga o 'tirdi va to 'satdan shu qadar bo 'shashib ketdiki, yerga guppa yiqilib, o 'lib qoladigandek bo 'ldi. Haqiqatan ham guppa yiqildi...* Sh.Xolmirzayev, Hayot abadiy.

2 To pound, to thunder. *Palovning bug 'i, shirin hidi guppa uradi.* Oybek, Tanlangan asarlar. The word **guppa** is interpreted as a homonym in the 2023 edition. Illustrative examples are also given according to their meanings. In the first sense, the adverb is a part of speech because it is similar in meaning to the words immediately is an instant and in the second sense, it refers to the meaning expressed by imitation of the situation, so its presentation as an imitative part of speech would be the basis for distinguishing the meanings of words from each other.

GURRA gur *Alijonning ikki oyog 'i osmonda charxpalak bo 'lib, yerga tushdi. Hatto yer changib ketdi. Davrada gurra qiyqiriq ko 'tarildi.* Mirmuhsin, Chiniqish. *Yigit-qizlar raisning mashinasi ko 'rinishi bilan gurra qo 'zg 'alishdi.* E.Usmonov, Yolqin.

The word “**gurra**” is usually associated with a verb. In such cases, it gives the meaning immediately, instantly and leads to the assumption that the adverb is a part of speech. But if you pay close attention to the sentences containing the word **gurra**, you can understand that the lexeme is a word named in imitation of a process that occurred suddenly, instantly. It should not be overlooked that the word **gurra** is formed from the word gur by the phenomenon of germination.

HIL-HIL To ripen and become soft. *Hil-hil pishgan yumshoq kabobni piyoz qo 'shib yeya boshladi.* Oybek, Ulug' yo'l. *Chanqab ketgan Haydar qovunni egarga urib, ikkiga bo 'ldi-yu, shoshganicha hil-hil pishgan bosvoldining suvini shimirdi.* Sh.Rashidov, Quدراتli to'lqin. The word “**hil-hil**” refers to a uniformly boiled, softly cooked dish. The simple variant of this word is not found in the Uzbek language. In the repeated case, the imitation corresponds to the word, since it is formed from an imitation of the process.

HILP-HILP to flutter. In the 2008 edition, this word is given only the interpretation of waving. There is no description of when, with which words it comes together and how it is used in practice. Also, an illustrative example with the participation of a lexeme is not given. In the common language, this lexeme is rarely used. It can be said that it is on the verge of depreciation. Students who do not know the meaning of the lexeme or users of a foreign language cannot obtain sufficient information through the explanation in the dictionary. This lexeme expresses an imitation of dresses with long hems or fabrics hanging from top to bottom moving in the wind. The 2023 edition includes an illustrative example. *Shunda beshkiyopg 'ich shamolda hilp-hilp etdi. Hilp-hilp eta-eta beshik ketilab uchib tushdi.* T.Murod, Otamdan qolgan dalalar.

JAVDIR-JAVDIR to glance, to look. *Ko 'zlarini javdiratmoq. Atrofga javdir-javdir boqib, qayerdan turib gapirishni mo 'ljallarkan, shovqin-so 'ron avj oldi.* A.Muxtor, Tug'ilish. The lexeme “**javdir-javdir**” is rarely used in the common language. The lexeme expresses the content created by imitating the state of looking around with a questioning gaze, with hope, with some purpose. The meaning of the lexeme can also be synonymous with the word **mo'lt-mo'lt**. The word “**mo'lt-mo'lt**” is used more widely. The meaning of **javdir-javdir** should be included with the reference *taql.s.* since it expresses an imitation of the eye position.

LASH-LUSH 1 *s.t.* All sorts of trifles. *Lash-lushlarimni ko 'tarib, Madalixon madrasasidan bir hujra olib, shunda tura boshladim.* M.Muhammadjonov, Turmush urinishlari. *Chol qovog 'i soliq holda lash-lushlarini aravadan oldi.* Oybek, Bolalik.

2 *s.t.* Skulls and intestines of slaughtered sheep or cattle. In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” (6 volumes), the lexeme “**lash-lush**” is described in two ways. Information

about which genus it belongs to is not provided. Through the explanation of the second meaning, it is understood that it belongs to the noun part of speech. The first meaning was interpreted as various small things. The lexeme denotes the name of things that are not of significant importance or the meaning named in imitation of the state of a pile of small things. Since it does not represent an object belonging to a specific type, it is correct to include it in dictionaries not as a noun, but as an imitative word.

PO'NG *s.t.* impure. *Aziza shu vaqtgacha qamchisidan qon tomib, so'zidan ilon po'st tashlagan dadasining ichi po'ng ekanini endi tushundi.* Shuhrat, Oltin zanglamas. The lexeme **po'ng** is rarely encountered in the common language. It is rarely seen in some dialects or written sources. The reflection of such lexemes in dictionaries is, of course, positive. Providing explanations and illustrative examples within a lexeme facilitates easy understanding of the content. In the explanation, it is emphasized that it is synonymous with the lexeme **po'k**. Since the main meaning of the lexeme "**po'k**" is known to many as an imitation of the sound produced by the light touch of objects, this word can be easily understood. In the illustrative example, the word **po'ng** expresses a figurative meaning. From this, it can be assumed that **po'ng** creates synonymy with the figurative form of the lexeme **po'k**.

PO'M *bol.* They stopped talking to each other, got into an argument; resentful. *Biz u bilan po'mmiz.* This word was formed by observers naming the situation when children were upset with each other. Since it is formed from the imitation of the process, the fact that this word is given as an imitative part of speech indicates that this word was named after imitation of children's speech.

QIR 1 hill. **2** edge. **3** building material. **4** qir(r) *taql.s.* It refers to the sound produced by friction between uneven or sticky objects. *Savag'ich qalamni "qirr" etib yurgizmoq. Mumlangan ipni "qirr" etib tortmoq.* In the 2023 edition, it is described that the lexeme **qir** can appear in four different places. In three places, it is understood that the place is a noun and the thing is a noun. In its fourth meaning, it is identified with the word **qirr**. The lexeme **qirr** expresses the sound produced by the friction of uneven or sticky objects against each other. This lexeme is given in the dictionary with the reference *taql.s.* This lexeme expresses a stronger sound than the word "**qir**". There is also a slight difference in the content of the lexemes. In future explanatory dictionaries, a separate description and illustrative example of the word "**qir**" will be given, which will make it even more convenient for students.

VISIR-VISIR *shv.* Whisper. *Ular "Yoqut boshqorong'i, Qodirjondan bolasi borga o'xshaydi", degan visir-visirni quloqdan quloqqa o'tkazib yuborishdi.* A.Abduvaliyev, Bizning yo'limiz. The word "**visir-visir**" in the meaning of gossip is similar to a noun and in naming it is similar to an imitative word in relation to an incomprehensible, low-pitched conversation process in speech. In the explanatory dictionary, the words "**shivir-shivir**" is cited as synonyms of this word, as well as in the illustrative example, it is correct to give this lexeme with the reference *taql.s.* since it expresses a name in relation to a low-toned speech sound.

G'IP to strangle tightly. *Hoy, menga qara! - dedi u burun kataklari pirpirab, - yoqangdan g'ip bo'g'ib, zo'ravonlik qilayotganda, derazadan ko'rib turganman.* O.Yoqubov, Larza. *Erining to'zg'igan sochlariga tikilib o'tiribdi-yu, lekin negadir ichidagini to'kib solishdan hayiqyapti. Bu hayiqish alami esa tomog'ini g'ip bo'g'moqda go'yo.* J.Abdullaxonov, To'fon. The lexeme "**g'ip**" usually forms a combination with a verb and according to this feature, it is close to the adverbial participle. However, the fact that this word is formed by imitating a quick, unexpected

and hard manner of action, embodying the process, indicates that the features of the part of speech imitating are higher.

G'ULT ayn. qult. *Ovqat uning tomog'idan, quvurdan o'tayotgan suvdek, g'ult-g'ult qilib o'tardi*¹. Shuhrat, Shinelli yillar. In the explanatory dictionary, the lexeme **g'ult** is identical in content to the lexeme qult. In the illustrative example, a repetitive example, a repetitive version is given. The word “**g'ult**” is somewhat outdated in terms of common usage and can be found in some dialects. Understanding the meaning of this word at first glance is a complex phenomenon. However, the meaning of the word can be fully understood through the description and illustrative example. The word **qult** is widely used. The sound produced by the word “**g'ult**” is weaker than the word “**qult**”. For this reason, a separate description of this lexeme, an example and the inclusion of the link *taql.s.* will make the meaning of the word clearer.

Results

In the explanatory dictionary, there are many words that express the meaning of imitation of a state or sound, fully representing the sign of an imitative part of speech. However, the category has not been clarified. Knowing the part of speech of a word is of great importance in understanding its meaning. Most users of the dictionary, if they are not aware of the science of linguistics, encounter a number of confusions in understanding the content of these lexemes. In the and, they almost do not use the word, not understanding the degree of significance and value of this word. The following list of lexemes belonging to the category of onomatopoeic words, but given without a special mark in the explanatory dictionary published in 2023, was formed.

1-

picture.

<i>ar-ar</i>	<i>baqir-buqur</i>	<i>bag'ir-bug'ur</i>	<i>bez-bez</i>	<i>bilang-bilang</i>	<i>biljing-biljing</i>
<i>biqir-biqir</i>	<i>dang</i>	<i>dangir-dungur</i>	<i>dang'ir-dung'ur</i>	<i>dikang-dikang</i>	<i>dik-dik</i>
<i>dikong-dikong</i>	<i>dikir-dikir</i>	<i>ding'ir-ding'ir</i>	<i>dir-dir</i>	<i>duv-duv</i>	<i>dud-dud</i>
<i>duk-duk</i>	<i>dukur-dukur</i>	<i>dup-dup</i>	<i>dupur-dupur</i>	<i>do'p-do'p</i>	<i>do'pir-do'pir</i>
<i>do'qir-do'qir</i>	<i>do'q-do'q</i>	<i>ding</i>	<i>gup-gup</i>	<i>guppa</i>	<i>guppa-guppa</i>
<i>gur</i>	<i>gurra</i>	<i>gusur-gusur</i>	<i>hap-hap</i>	<i>hilp-hilp</i>	<i>hil-hil</i>
<i>hingir-hingir</i>	<i>huv</i>	<i>javdir-javdir</i>	<i>jaz-buz</i>	<i>jaz-jaz</i>	<i>jaz-juz</i>
<i>jarang-jurung</i>	<i>jiz-jiz</i>	<i>jiz</i>	<i>jiz-biz</i>	<i>jimir</i>	<i>jimir-jimir</i>
<i>jing</i>	<i>jingir-jingir</i>	<i>jiq-jiq</i>	<i>kappa-kappa</i>	<i>kasir-kasir</i>	<i>lash-lush</i>
<i>laq-luq</i>	<i>lik-lik</i>	<i>lik</i>	<i>lip</i>	<i>lip-lip</i>	<i>lippa</i>
<i>liq</i>	<i>lo'k-lo'k</i>	<i>lo'p</i>	<i>lo'q</i>	<i>lo'q-lo'q</i>	<i>papaq</i>
<i>parr-parr</i>	<i>patir-patir</i>	<i>pil-pil</i>	<i>pir-pir</i>	<i>pirq-pirq</i>	<i>pis-pis</i>
<i>pitpiliq</i>	<i>pitpildi</i>	<i>pichir</i>	<i>pichir-pichir</i>	<i>piqir-piqir</i>	<i>piq-piq</i>
<i>pov-pov</i>	<i>pop-pop</i>	<i>po'k-po'k</i>	<i>po'ng</i>	<i>po'm</i>	<i>qaldir-quldur</i>

¹ O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. 6 jildli. – Toshkent: “G'afur G'ulom” nashriyoti, 2023.

<i>qalt-qalt</i>	<i>qasira-qusur</i>	<i>qasir-qusur</i>	<i>qaqir-ququr</i>	<i>qah-qah</i>	<i>qiy-chuv</i>
<i>qilt</i>	<i>qimir</i>	<i>qimir-qimir</i>	<i>qir</i>	<i>qirt-qirt</i>	<i>qirs-qirs</i>
<i>qir-qir</i>	<i>qisir-qisir</i>	<i>qitir-qitir</i>	<i>qiqir-qiqir</i>	<i>qult-qult</i>	<i>qulq-qulq</i>
<i>qur-qur</i>	<i>quq-quq</i>	<i>tapira-tupur</i>	<i>tap-tap</i>	<i>tap-tup</i>	<i>tasira-tusur</i>
<i>taq-tuq</i>	<i>ting'ir-ting'ir</i>	<i>ting'-ting'</i>	<i>tipir-tipir</i>	<i>tiq-tiq</i>	<i>tors</i>
<i>tors-tors</i>	<i>vang-vang</i>	<i>visir-visir</i>	<i>yilt</i>	<i>yal-yal</i>	<i>zip</i>
<i>zir-zir</i>	<i>zirq-zirq</i>	<i>g'iyh</i>	<i>g'iyq</i>	<i>g'ilq</i>	<i>g'ing'ir- g'ing'ir</i>
<i>g'ing'-g'ing'</i>	<i>g'ip</i>	<i>g'ippa</i>	<i>g'it</i>	<i>g'irch</i>	<i>g'ichir</i>
<i>g'ich-g'ich</i>	<i>g'ir-g'ir</i>	<i>g'ult</i>	<i>g'o'ldir- g'o'ldir</i>	<i>shaldir- shuldir</i>	<i>shap</i>
<i>sharaq- sharaq</i>	<i>sharaq- shuruq</i>	<i>sharr</i>	<i>shart-shurt</i>	<i>sharq</i>	<i>shatira- shutur</i>
<i>shaqir- shuqur</i>	<i>shaq-shuq</i>	<i>shilp</i>	<i>shirq</i>	<i>shig'</i>	<i>shiqir</i>
<i>shov-shuv</i>	<i>sho'p</i>	<i>chak-chak</i>	<i>chalp-chalp</i>	<i>chalp-chulp</i>	<i>chap</i>
<i>chap-chap</i>	<i>charaq- charaq</i>	<i>chars-chars</i>	<i>chars-churs</i>	<i>chag'-chug'</i>	<i>chip-chip</i>
<i>chir</i>	<i>chirk-chirk</i>	<i>chirs-chirs</i>	<i>chirt-chirt</i>	<i>chirq-chirq</i>	<i>chir-chir</i>
<i>chitir-chitir</i>	<i>chiqir-chiqir</i>	<i>chiq-chiq</i>	<i>chig'-chig'</i>	<i>chuvur</i>	<i>chuvur- chuvur</i>
<i>chuv-chuv</i>	<i>churq</i>	<i>chug'ur- chug'ur</i>	<i>cho'lp- cho'lp²</i>		

1-picture. Lexemes given without special link in the explanatory dictionary published in 2023. The content of the above-mentioned words, the illustrative examples given to them, show that they belong to the category of onomatopoeic words. Also, most of them are repeated onomatopoeic words. In some places, the simple form of these words is included as an imitative part of speech. However, this repetitive type also does not lead to the conclusion that it belongs to the part of speech of onomatopoeia. The reason is that in some repetitive types of imitations, there are cases when a noun or adverb is transferred to a part of speech. In subsequent editions of explanatory dictionaries, it is necessary to pay attention to the inclusion of the above onomatopoeic words with a special onomatopoeic reference.

Conclusion

The constant renewal of dictionaries, the expansion of their lexical composition and the improvement of their usability are a requirement of the times. An important task is to clarify the categories of words belonging to the Uzbek language, a critical approach and an assessment of their current activities. When we observed the explanatory dictionaries published during the years of independence, including the explanatory dictionary published in 2023, we witnessed that the description of onomatopoeic words or illustrative examples are not given in themselves, but are directed at words with similar meanings or are included incompletely. It is necessary to clarify not only onomatopoeic words, but also other parts of speech. Expanding the number of

² O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. 6 jildli. – Toshkent: “G'afur G'ulom” nashriyoti, 2023.

onomatopoeic words in explanatory dictionaries based on the study of the national language, dialects and literary works will become the basis for increasing the possibility of using onomatopoeic words in the future and the development of the literary language.

In the explanatory dictionary published in 2023, the total number of onomatopoeic words with link is **269/47%**, while the total number of onomatopoeic words without link is **298/53%**. In explanatory dictionaries, words that are not included in the form of onomatopoeic word and fully reflect its features, are more numerous than words included with a special link. In subsequent editions of the explanatory dictionary, a link to these words should also be included. Onomatopoeic words without a link were given as a recommendation.

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